

graphia

GRAPHIA

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities

Work Package WP2
SSH Knowledge Graph (KG)

Deliverable D2.1
GRAPHIA Ontology

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List of Abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
KG	Knowledge Graph
LOT	Linked Open Terms
ORSD	Ontology Requirement Specification Document
OWL	Web Ontology Language
SAMOD	Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

Executive Summary

GRAPHIA aims at developing innovative tooling for Social Science and Humanities researchers. One of these innovations is the creation of the GRAPHIA SSH Knowledge Graph, which should provide a unique entry point for researchers to retrieve datasets from multiple domains and sources of information. Creating such a global Knowledge Graph requires designing and adopting a common data model to align the different data sources together. This document describes the development of this common data model, the GRAPHIA Ontology.

In the first section, we highlight the technical choices that drive this work, i.e. the technical architecture, described in Deliverable D2.2 and a state of the art on ontology development methodology and existing interoperability frameworks. The second section describes the scope and conceptual design of the GRAPHIA Ontology based on the choice made from the state-of-the-art analysis. The third section describes our methodology to develop the GRAPHIA Ontology, i.e. requirement collection, testing methods, publication and governance of the ontology. The fourth and final section provides an overview of the results of the development work, including an analysis of the initial data sources to be interconnected and of the potential additional candidate sources.

1. Introduction

1.1. GRAPHIA Knowledge Graph: a federation of graphs.

The GRAPHIA project aims to revolutionise the accessibility, integration, and analysis of knowledge in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) community by constructing the first comprehensive **SSH Knowledge Graph** (KG). This KG will act as a unified entry point to many SSH data sources and knowledge graphs, providing researchers with a gateway to access data coming from multiple disciplines.

To align these heterogeneous and distributed resources, two main options can be considered: 1. **harvest and aggregate** the content of the data sources into one unique KG, similar to the approach taken by OpenAIRE and GoTRIPLE, which would enable us to align these resources to a unique common ontology; 2. **design a light interoperability layer**, a simple “top level ontology”, to connect resources managed and controlled by the communities building these resources into a federation of Knowledge Graphs.

The federative approach has been identified as the core architectural principle for the design of the GRAPHIA SSH Knowledge Graph. The motivation for this architectural choice is clearly listed in the companion deliverable D2.2. To summarise, the federation enables each resource to remain autonomously managed as long as it provides its content through a common interoperability framework. This approach also eases the process of integrating new resources into the federation. The harvest and aggregate approach would be too costly to implement and to maintain as the central graph would increase commensurably in size as we add new resources. Furthermore, adding a new resource would require developing dedicated interfaces and extending the data acquisition platform developed in T2.3. This architectural choice has a major impact on the work of T2.1 presented in this deliverable.

1.2. Purpose and Scope of the Deliverable

To achieve semantic interoperability between these sources, we need to have interoperability frameworks that enforce syntactic and semantic consistency, allowing the data to have qualitative linking and high discovery. Such interoperability

frameworks need a defined common data model/vocabulary to allow our systems to communicate. KGs implemented based on formal knowledge representation models known as ontologies are more consistent and grounded. Ontologies define the objects in the domain (for example, publications or authors in SSH), their properties (such as a publication date), and their relationships (such as authoredBy). By sharing the semantic modeling structure and vocabulary, ontologies give the data the syntactic and semantic consistency needed for interoperability.

The aim of the T2.1 is to propose a data model, the GRAPHIA Ontology, to enable the alignment between multiple heterogeneous data sources and cover the whole SSH domain. SSH is a broad research field that includes many diverse subdomains. Building a single ontology capable of representing this diversity is therefore a challenging task. Furthermore, developing a common ontology for the SSH Knowledge Graph would require each knowledge graph to align themselves to this new model and update their content.

This document outlines the work carried out in Task 2.1 to develop the framework to design the GRAPHIA ontology and describes its main components. The document is structured as follows. In the following section, we provide relevant background regarding ontology design methodologies and existing interoperability framework. Section 2 details the GRAPHIA Ontology covering the scope definition, the implementation choices and the conceptual design based on the implementation choices. Section 3 details the approach adopted for the development of the GRAPHIA Ontology i.e. requirements collection, testing methodology, publication and documentation process and the governance and the release process. Section 4 describes the practical work done to develop the first version of the GRAPHIA ontology. This includes the analysis of the resources considered for this first integration, their alignment with SKG-O, and the resulting SPARQL and REST API calls based on two selected Competency Questions. Section 5 provides the conclusions and highlights the aspects that require further work in subsequent stages of the project.

1.3. State of the art

This section provides a state of the art on ontology design methodologies and interoperability frameworks that would support the development of the SSH KG.

1.3.1. Ontology design methodologies

Several methodologies for designing ontologies have been proposed such as METHONTOLOGY (Fernández-López et al., 1997), On-To-Knowledge (Staab et al., 2001), DILIGENT (Pinto et al., 2004), the “Ontology Development 101” guide (Noy and McGuinness, 2001), NeOn (Suárez-Figueroa et al., 2015) and SAMOD (Peroni, 2016).

The Linked Open Terms¹ (LOT; Poveda-Villalón et al., 2022) integrates these different approaches to ontology development into a coherent framework, designed to align with standard workflows in software engineering and academic research projects. Following agile development practices, LOT adopts an iterative process inspired by the Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development (SAMOD; Peroni, 2017)² methodology. In the LOT methodology, each cycle consists of four steps (represented by the four blue rectangles in Figure 1).

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755>

² https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-54627-8_5

Figure 1: Flowchart illustrating the activities, artefacts and actors involved in LOT
*Ont.Devel. represents ontology developer

In more details, these four steps are as follows:

1. The **ontology requirements specification**: In this first activity, ontologists, domain experts and intended users agree on use cases and the purpose of the ontology. This will lead to functional requirements, which can be expressed in a list of **competency questions** or statements that, alongside the **purpose of the ontology**, will be put in an Ontology Requirement Specification Document (ORSD). This document is in itself quite similar to the *modelet*³ in SAMOD as it guides the team through the implementation activity.
2. **The implementation**: This part concerns the actual implementation of the ontology using a formal language. This activity is iterative: in each cycle, parts of the requirements in the ORSD are first conceptualized into ontological

³“A *modelet* is a stand-alone model describing a particular domain. By definition, a modelet does not include entities from other models and it is not included in other models.” (see <https://essepuntato.it/samod/>)

aspects, then are written in OWL (Web Ontology Language), refined with the import of existing terms, and finally subjected to a series of automated tests. These tests include the detection of bad practices, verification against the ORSD and the conceptual model and validation against test cases expressed as SPARQL queries with expected results derived from the competency questions. This part of the development cycle is similar to continuous integration, as the evaluation step ensures the quality of the ontology while it is being developed. The activity is repeated until all tests are successfully passed.

3. **The publication:** Once the evaluation of the ontology passes the evaluation phase, it can be tagged as a release candidate. The ontology is documented and then published on the web; otherwise, an additional implementation cycle is carried out.
4. **The maintenance:** This activity allows a new development cycle to begin whenever additional requirements arise. In such cases, the process restarts from the ontology requirements specification stage. If a bug or any other error is identified (including errors in the documentation), the cycle can resume from step 2 or step 3 in order to apply the correction and publish an updated version.

The methodology's website⁴ provides an overview of each activity, a list of recommended tools, examples of projects that have adopted the methodology, and a link to their GitHub repository containing schemas and document templates. In addition, A FAIR by design approach, LOT4FAIR has been proposed in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT⁵ project (Poveda-Villalon M. et al., 2023)⁶. The LOT4FAIR methodology extends the LOT methodology considering the various guidelines to improve the FAIRness level of the resulting ontologies for each ontology development phase or activity, therefore, implement the FAIR principles for semantic artefacts. The LOT methodology was unanimously chosen, within the Workpackage, as a coherent framework and process to follow in this ontology development activity.

Decision record - 1
Use the LOT methodology to support the development of the GRAPHIA Ontology

⁴ <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>

⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10551054>

1.3.2. Interoperability Frameworks

Interoperability frameworks provide the conceptual, organisational, semantic, and technical foundations required for linking heterogeneous data sources across institutions and domains. In the context of GRAPHIA, the interoperability frameworks are important because they define the standards, protocols, and architectural principles that support consistent data exchange and semantic alignment across diverse SSH resources. This section summarises the main interoperability frameworks reviewed and highlights elements that inform the design choices for the GRAPHIA Knowledge Graph.

European Interoperability Framework (EIF)

The European Interoperability Framework⁷ defines a general-purpose model to support interoperability across public administrations in the EU. It distinguishes four layers – legal, organisational, semantic, and technical – and provides 12 principles and 47 recommendations that promote openness, reuse of standards, and transparent data exchange.

While EIF is not tailored to research infrastructures, several of its principles are directly applicable to the GRAPHIA context, notably the emphasis on open standards, common data models, and structured approaches to semantic and syntactic interoperability. However, many administrative and legal components of EIF fall outside the scope of research-centric KGs.

EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF)

EOSC-IF⁸, inspired by EIF described previously, is designed specifically for research infrastructures and offers a structured framework to enable FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research outputs across disciplines. It introduces the concept of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs), each with persistent identifiers, rich metadata, provenance descriptions, and relations to other objects. EOSC-IF also provides a high-level reference architecture covering PID services, metadata

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf

⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K. et al., EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

registries, semantic artefact management, security frameworks, and minimal metadata for discovery.

EOSC-IF is particularly relevant for GRAPHIA due to its focus on semantic coherence, persistent identifiers, machine-actionable metadata, and cross-domain discoverability. Its main limitation in the SSH context is the substantial metadata burden and uneven readiness of many SSH data providers to generate FDO-compliant descriptions.

Global Open Research Commons – International Model (GORC-IM)

The GORC International Model⁹ takes a holistic view of research interoperability, covering governance, access rules, sustainability, human capacity, interoperability layers, standards, ICT infrastructure, services, tools, and research objects. It provides a shared vocabulary and reference model rather than a prescriptive implementation.

For GRAPHIA, GORC-IM offers valuable guidance on governance, access policies, and sustainability considerations relevant to federated infrastructures. However, it does not define concrete semantic or technical mechanisms and thus must be complemented with more operational frameworks such as EOSC-IF or SKG-IF.

Cross-Disciplinary Interoperability Framework (CDIF)

Developed in the Horizon Europe WorldFAIR project¹⁰, CDIF¹¹ addresses interoperability across disciplinary boundaries by defining a small, domain-agnostic metadata “lingua franca” composed of five core profiles: Discovery, Access, Controlled Vocabularies, Data Integration, and Universals (time, place, units). These profiles are built on widely adopted web standards (e.g. JSON-LD, Schema.org, SKOS, DCAT, DDI-CDI).

CDIF is highly aligned with GRAPHIA’s objectives, particularly the need to integrate heterogeneous SSH resources without forcing all providers to adopt a single rich domain ontology. It provides practical crosswalks, lightweight profiles, and implementation principles that support scalable metadata harmonisation. The main

⁹https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Global-Open-Research-Commons-International-Model-version-1.1-Model-documentation_FINAL.pdf

¹⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/the-project/>

¹¹ <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html>

challenges relate to metadata overhead and uneven tooling maturity for some profiles.

Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF)

SKG-IF¹² is an interoperability framework developed to interconnect existing Scientific Knowledge Graphs such as OpenCitation and OpenAIRE. SKG-IF is therefore designed for building a lightweight interoperability layer between knowledge graphs and is therefore the most operational and technically aligned framework for GRAPHIA. It provides:

- a shared semantic data model for research products, agents, data sources, grants, topics, and venues;
- the SKG-IF Ontology (SKG-O)¹³, which reuses stable entities from existing ontologies, such as Dublin Core, DCAT, FOAF, PROV, schema.org, ...;
- JSON-LD contexts for standardised serialisation;
- SHACL shapes for semantic validation;
- examples, test suites, and reference implementations.

SKG-IF directly addresses semantic interoperability challenges in knowledge graph environments and offers practical mechanisms for aligning heterogeneous research metadata. Among all frameworks reviewed, SKG-IF offers the closest technical fit for the SSH KG architecture envisaged in GRAPHIA.

To summarise, the interoperability frameworks reviewed vary in scope, from broad governance models (GORC-IM) to operational metadata infrastructures (EOSC-IF, SKG-IF) and cross-domain metadata profiles (CDIF). For GRAPHIA, three frameworks are particularly relevant:

- **SKG-IF** (core technical and semantic foundation for federated scientific KGs)
- **EOSC-IF** (persistent identifiers, FDOs, metadata registries, FAIR compliance)
- **CDIF** (lightweight cross-domain metadata profiles enabling pragmatic interoperability)

These frameworks highlight key considerations for designing the GRAPHIA Knowledge Graph, including the use of shared semantic models, persistent

¹² <https://skg-if.github.io/>

¹³ <https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/ontology/current/skg-o.html>

identifiers, structured metadata, and interoperable APIs. The two operational models, i.e. CDIF and SKG-IF overlap on various features (e.g. use of JSON-LD, common vocabularies, mappings,...). However, the most appropriate interoperability framework for GRAPHIA is clearly SKG-IF which has been designed to create federations of Knowledge Graphs and is currently implemented in various projects. It is therefore the obvious choice as an interoperability framework for this task. It entails that the GRAPHIA Ontology will be based on the SKG-O ontology.

Decision record - 2

Use SKG-IF as the foundation for the GRAPHIA Ontology

This decision implies potential limitations and shortcomings such as the dependency on the SKG-IF adoption by the KG joining the federation and the assumption that SKG-O is generic enough to cover the different types of data from the various SSH domains and can be extended easily to increase the coverage.

2. The GRAPHIA Ontology

2.1. Scope of the ontology and initial KG to be aligned

The GRAPHIA Ontology aims to provide the semantic backbone of the SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG). Its primary role is to ensure that the different data sources and Knowledge Graphs involved in the project, whether developed within GRAPHIA or maintained by external providers, can interoperate through a shared conceptual model and a common vocabulary.

From the outset, the **ontology's scope** was therefore not limited to a single data source or internal graph, but conceived as a **cross-cutting semantic layer** spanning the entire federated architecture of the SSH KG. This vision reflects a key architectural decision of the project: the SSH Knowledge Graph would not be built as a single, aggregated repository, but as a federation of autonomous, domain-specific Knowledge Graphs interlinked through a common interoperability framework (see Figure 2 below). Such a federated approach allows each partner or infrastructure to

maintain its own governance, update policies, and internal schema, while enabling discovery, linking, and analytics across distributed graphs.

* Future integrations: The federation will expand to include E-RIHS DIGILAB, Matilda, RelReSearch, and other domain-specific graphs.

Figure 2: Federated architecture of the SSH Knowledge Graph (GRAPHIA SSH KG)

This choice provides multiple advantages in terms of scalability, sustainability and semantic coherence compared to aggregating all data into a single graph. This modularity enables the independent evolution of the various KGs without requiring complex central ingestion and transformation processes. It also simplifies the integration of new sources, since each node in the federation can expose its data through standard interfaces, without the need to develop dedicated import connectors and guaranteeing that this way data stay always up-to-date. Each graph remains responsible for the provenance, persistence, and quality of its own data, while the federation layer provides discovery, alignment, and linking services across them.

To support this, we designed a layered architecture, described in Figure 2, to support the development of the SSH KG with three main components:

- (1) the **Ontology Layer**, defining the semantic model (GRAPHIA Ontology aligned with SKG-O) and relying extensively on the use of mappings and crosswalks in a machine actionable format (e.g. SSSOM) and extensions of the SKG-O model;

(2) the **Interoperability Layer**, based on SKG-IF and enabling cross-graph alignment and discovery relying on a mixed set of interfaces (REST API, SPARQL,...);

(3) the **Federated Knowledge Graphs**, including the GoTriple KG (managed by GRAPHIA) and external SSH KGs (e.g., EHRI, GESIS, OpenCitations, ORKG).

To start the work on the SSH KG federation, we identified four main resources to establish the initial version of the ontology. The GoTriple Knowledge Graph (GoTriple KG), developed within GRAPHIA, is the first and main KG to be fully aligned with the GRAPHIA Ontology. It represents the SSH-specific hub of the federation, extending the GoTriple platform with a new semantic layer expressed in RDF. Beyond GoTriple, the GRAPHIA Ontology defines the alignment strategy for three other external production SSH Knowledge Graphs: ORKG, GESIS and OpenCitations. These three other external resources have been selected based on their maturity as production KG.

Decision record - 3
Focus on four initial data sources: GoTriple, ORKG, OpenCitations and GESIS KG

The architecture is designed to scale beyond these initial core partners (GoTriple, OpenCitations, ORKG, GESIS). It will support the federation of the broader ecosystem of domain-specific graphs defined in the Grant Agreement, including Matilda (bibliometrics), RelReSearch (Religious studies), and E-RIHS DIGILAB (Heritage Science), paving the way for further integrations as the ecosystem expands.

In summary, the GRAPHIA Ontology serves three complementary purposes:

1. To **define a shared semantic model** ensuring interoperability across SSH Knowledge Graphs;
2. To **provide alignment rules and validation mechanisms** in line with SKG-IF and SKG-O;
3. To **support the federated architecture of the SSH KG**, connecting GRAPHIA-managed and external graphs through a coherent semantic layer.

This layered vision, comprising the ontology, interoperability, and federation levels, is described in more detail in Deliverable D2.2 (Technical Architecture), which

formalises the technical and governance framework derived from this ontological design.

In cases where a participating KG doesn't support the SKG-IF interoperability framework, the GRAPHIA ontology can be specifically extended to include dedicated mappings and alignment modules with its native data model.

Finally, for graphs implemented on semantic triple stores federation can be technically achieved through SPARQL 1.1 Federated Query, which allows queries to be executed across multiple distributed endpoints. This way, a SPARQL query can dynamically retrieve and combine results from different knowledge graphs, without the need to physically aggregate their data.

2.2. Conceptual design

As detailed above, we chose to leverage the SKG-IF for the proposed SSH KG. This interoperability framework has been developed in the context of the RDA¹⁴ to address the need to interconnect different existing Scientific Knowledge Graphs. It is refined and implemented in the context of several other European-funded projects – i.e. SciLake, GraspOS, OStrails and LUMEN – and infrastructures such as OpenAIRE, OpenCitations, GoTriple, and the Novi-Sad University CRIS system.

Based on our initial design, this interoperability framework is a perfect fit for the development of the SSH KG federation (see figure 3 below). In this figure, we describe the interconnection between four SSH data resources, i.e. GoTriple, OpenCitation, GESIS KG and ORKG.

¹⁴<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg/activity/>

Figure 3: SSH Knowledge Graphs federated by the SKG-Interoperability Framework through the alignment with the SKG Ontology, SKG-O.

The implementation of SKG-IF requires the different data sources to provide a dedicated SKG-IF REST API which will enable to query the different KGs and to get the answers into a common format (JSON-LD) and aligned on SKG-O. It enables to interconnect existing independent KGs without having to change them e.g. by integrating the alignment with a central ontology. The connection to the SKG-IF REST API requires to perform mappings between the data model of the resource to be aligned and the SKG-O. These mappings will be used to support the conversion of the query results into the SKG-O aligned JSON-LD output.

In the context of this work, the GRAPHIA Ontology is built upon the SKG-Ontology (SKG-O) and is composed of

1. necessary extensions of SKG-O and
2. the collection of mappings between the data models of existing KGs and SKG-O

The integration of several KGs into the federation will require first defining non transformative alignments with SKG-O and identifying the gaps in the data model to accurately represent the content of the data source. These will allow us to use the

existing extension process proposed by SKG-IF¹⁵. These extensions could be aligned under a common namespace, forming the GRAPHIA Ontology as an extension for SSH of SKG Ontology as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: GRAPHIA Ontology as an extension of SKG-O

This approach will be evaluated as we move forward with the integration of various data resources.

3. Our approach to develop the ontology

In this section, we present our approach to designing and developing the ontology. To develop the GRAPHIA ontology, we chose to ground our approach in the LOT Methodology (see section 1.3.1). The first step of the LOT methodology is the **ontology requirements specification**, during which we define the scope of the ontology (see section 2.1) and the competency questions (see section 3.1). The second phase of the LOT methodology, i.e. the **implementation** is presented in section 4. We then lay out the foundation of the testing of our ontology (see section 3.2). Finally, the third step of the LOT methodology deals with the definition of a publication strategy (third step of the LOT methodology, see section 3.3) and a governance model for the maintenance phase of LOT methodology (see section 3.4).

¹⁵ <https://skg-if.github.io/extensions/>

3.1. Requirements collection: competency questions

Before starting the design of an ontology, it is necessary to identify the set of queries the ontology should support, commonly referred to as Competency Questions (CQs). This preparatory work, carried out during the **ontology requirements specification** phase of the LOT methodology together with ontology scoping, is essential: on the one hand, it provides a set of tests to evaluate whether the ontology is fit for purpose; on the other hand, it helps to identify the concepts and relations that would be necessary to answer these queries.

Competency Questions are natural language questions that are collected by the users of the ontology and the subsequent Knowledge Graph, such as: “*Given a publication PID, find all articles that cite it plus those cited in the publication itself*”. These natural language questions should then be transformed into SPARQL queries that would be performed on the KG. The main challenge in collecting these queries is that they must be formulated across four heterogeneous knowledge graphs: GoTriple, ORKG, OpenCitations, and GESIS, which constitute our initial federation target. As a result, the CQs need to reflect use cases that can span multiple KGs rather than apply to a single source (see section 4.1 below for detailed description of the resources).

To collect these CQs, we worked with Task 2.1 contributors and with the GRAPHIA use cases participants during multiple workshops, including a focussed session during the Innovation Prototyping Lab (IPL), organised in Zagreb¹⁶. The CQs were collected in a shared Google spreadsheet to allow for asynchronous contributions. The table is structured as follows:

1. CQ identifier
2. The Competency Question in natural language
3. The name of the proposer
4. The expected answer, i.e. type of information that should be returned
5. The “core” KG involved
6. Other KGs (link with use-cases)
7. Use case description
8. Concepts identified from the analysis of the question
9. The resulting SPARQL query
10. Comments

¹⁶ <https://lumenproject.eu/registration-ipl-2025/>

11. Information about the CQs' status, name of the reviewers of the CQs, complexity and priority

In total, we collected 70 CQs, and analysed most of them to identify those that are easiest to implement and test, which will be used to create and test the first version of the ontology. Fourteen of these have been identified as top priority and will form the initial pool of tests for the ontology. A list of the collected CQs is provided in Annex A with information about their priority and the KG covered by these CQs whenever available. To define the level of priority, we used two main criteria: 1- the level of complexity of the competency question to identify an initial of “simple cases” to test the approach and 2- the coverage of the target of Knowledge Graphs (see section 4.1) i.e. ensuring that all KGs are inter-related with the initial set of CQs.

3.2. Testing

To develop the GRAPHIA Ontology, we are relying on the Competency Questions collected. The CQs will enable us to identify the necessary concepts and relations for answering the queries. Although crucial in the design phase, the CQs have a central role for testing the ontology. Indeed, each version of the ontology will be tested against a pre-defined set of CQs. The quality of the query results will be assessed to determine whether the ontology passes or not. These tests can be automated to ease the development process.

The adoption of SKG-IF provides us with the possibility to also test the quality of the data collected from the SKG-IF API using SHACL, a W3C standard developed to test the compliance of graphs into a defined graph pattern/structure, called SHAPes Constraint Language (SHACL)¹⁷.

3.3. Publication and documentation

A major step of the LOT Methodology is the publication of the ontology. Ontologies are artefacts of the web therefore they must be published. Usually, ontologies are published as code in repositories such as github. SKG-O is published on github and documented using the Live Ontology Documentation Environment (LODE)¹⁸ and

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

¹⁸ <https://essepuntato.it/lode/>

Widoco¹⁹. As GRAPHIA Ontology is composed of extensions and mappings with SKG-O, we will use the SKG-IF github repository to publish any extensions as one of the final publication environments. In addition to the github repository, we will investigate the possibility to publish the ontology into a relevant ontology repository which will provide access to the ontology and its content (i.e. concepts and relations) through a REST API for programmatic access.

3.4. Governance & release plan

When building a federation, governance is a major component to consider. In our case, governance can be considered at different levels:

- **At the federation level:** Clear and transparent rules for onboarding and integrating new data resources into the federation must be established. These should include, at minimum:
 - Alignment with the SKG-IF framework and modelling principles.
 - Provision of an SKG-IF-compliant REST API.
 - Adherence to documented technical and semantic integration guidelines.
 - Defined responsibilities and expectations for federation members, including update cycles and data quality obligations.
 - Processes for evaluating, approving, and monitoring new federation participants.
- **At the ontology level:** A comprehensive set of ontology governance guidelines should be defined to support the full lifecycle of the ontology. These should address:
 - Standard processes for proposing, reviewing, and approving extensions or modifications.
 - Maintenance and update procedures, including release schedules and communication practices.
 - Version control policies, including the management of stable and versioned IRIs.
 - Publication and distribution policies for ontology releases.
 - participants

¹⁹ <https://github.com/dgarijo/Widoco>

- **At the SKG-O extension level:** Each SKG-O extension should be managed and governed by the data resource. Governance should include:
 - Clear guidelines for updating, maintaining, and deprecating extension content.
 - Alignment with the overarching SKG-IF principles and ontology governance framework.
 - Defined approval workflows for proposing changes to an extension.
 - Documentation and metadata requirements to ensure transparency and reusability.
 - Versioning and publishing practices consistent with the core SKG-O ontology.

These guidelines and rules have not been defined at the time of writing and should be developed in a later phase of the development. At the current time, any output of this work will be hosted in the project Gitlab. Once validated, any major changes will also be added to the SKG-IF github repository (i.e. extensions,...)

4. Development of the ontology

In this section, we describe the outcomes of the first iteration of the GRAPHIA Ontology design.

4.1. Analysis of the initial data sources

To start the development of the GRAPHIA Ontology and of the first version of the GRAPHIA SSH Knowledge Graph, we selected four initial data sources to be integrated: GoTriple, ORKG, GESIS KG and OpenCitation. In the following paragraphs, we analyse these four initial resources.

4.1.1. GoTriple

As indicated in D2.2 Graphia Deliverable (*Technical Architecture*), a new companion service will be implemented with graph technologies, the GoTriple KG. Based on a Semantic Web compliant triple store, it will not only expose GoTriple's **metadata of SSH resources** (Documents, Author's Profiles, Projects, Datasets, Semantic Artefacts, Multimedia) in graph format but also include descriptions of datasets acquired through tools and instruments, as defined in the GRAPHIA WP3 workpackage (Innovative Solutions and Instruments for the SSH KG) as well as **entities** extracted

from the full text of documents by AI and NLP-powered services developed in GRAPHIA in the context of the WP4 workpackage (Artificial Intelligence Solutions for the SSH KG).

Data in this graph will be formalised by the means of the TRIPLE Ontology that is aligned with SKG-O (see section 4.2.1). A SKG-IF compliant REST API is being developed and will also be provided, ensuring full compatibility with the GRAPHIA Ontology modelisation and the SSH KG requirements.

The diagram below shows the current GoTriple data model used for managing SSH resources metadata.

Figure 5: GoTriple data model

It proposes four main classes describing the different types of entities collected in the graph i.e. Document, Dataset, Semantic Artefact, Multimedia. These classes of entities are then connected to either a Project or an Author or both.

4.1.2. Open Citations

OpenCitations provides free, open access to **bibliographic and citation data**. The development team is currently advocating SKG-IF, as its Director Silvio Peroni has co-authored the specification, and plans to support SKG-IF in OpenCitations with the

release of a SKG-IF compliant REST API in 2026. Open Citations already offers a SPARQL endpoint²⁰ to query its data. Therefore, its federation in the SSH KG can be achieved by exploiting SPARQL Federated Queries and also including the GRAPHIA Ontology ad-hoc mappings with its data model. At the same time, it is important to point out that OpenCitations includes a large amount of non-SSH resources, so the strategy for its integration must take into account how to filter out non-relevant content for the SSH KG.

The OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM) is shown below in Figure 6.

Figure 6: OpenCitations data model

This data model is based on multiple ontologies such as FABIO, CITO, PRO, BIRO, FOAF and datacite.

4.1.3. GESIS KG

The GESIS Knowledge Graph (GESIS KG) integrates and links metadata of social science scholarly resources like datasets, publications, survey variables, survey instruments, and computational methods. Multiple link identification activities are employed to provide a comprehensive interlinked graph which includes manually

²⁰ <https://sparql.opencitations.net/>

curated links as well as links extracted by automatic NLP-based link detection pipelines. The data model of the GESIS KG is based on the GESIS KG Ontology which reuses types and properties from established standards such as schema.org, and the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI), ensuring interoperability, machine-readability, and reusability of data on the Web. To leverage domain-specific content and relations not covered by the reused vocabularies, the ontology is extended with additional classes and properties.

The GESIS KG is accessible via its SPARQL endpoint²¹, and it is planned to provide an SKG-IF compliant API.

4.1.4. Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)

The Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) provides structured and interconnected research findings to make scientific knowledge more accessible, discoverable and actionable. Structured paper data is organised in *contributions*, which capture the knowledge of a paper, i.e. research problem, materials, methods and results. But the user is free to add further properties for contributions. From papers only metadata that is actually used within the ORKG is recorded, any other metadata is ignored. From a set of papers, which address the same research problem, a *comparison* can be created to facilitate rankings of methods, compiling state-of-the-art literature overviews or comparing research on geographical differences. The ORKG KG is accessible via its SPARQL endpoint²², and it is planned to provide an SKG-IF compliant API.

4.2. Alignment with SKG-O

The first step to create the GRAPHIA Ontology is to establish mappings between the different data models of the data sources of interest. To collect and represent the mappings, we are leveraging the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM) model²³ as recommended by the Research Data Alliance FAIR Mapping WG^{24,25}. Using SSSOM enables to document the mappings for evaluation and reuse with an extended set of metadata and enforce the use of explicit predicates such as

²¹ <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>

²² <https://orkg.org/sparql/>

²³ <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

²⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/activity/>

²⁵ <https://mapping-commons.github.io/rda-fair-mappings/>

owl:sameas, owl:equivalentClass, and SKOS-related properties such as broader, narrower, exactMatch, closeMatch, relatedMatch which provide less semantic constraints compared to OWL relations. In addition, the tabular format used by SSSOM can be transformed into RDF which makes the mappings easy machine-actionable. Mappings have been collected in an extended spreadsheet with a subset of the SSSOM metadata elements. In the table below, we are presenting the mappings in reduced format to ease the reading.

4.2.1. GoTriple

GoTriple has already embraced in full the guidelines of the SKG-IF initiatives. To start with, its data model (the TRIPLE Ontology²⁶) maps SKG-O concepts for its classes, as described in table 1 below.

Subject_id	Predicate_id	Target_id	Comment
triple:Document	skos:exactMatch	fabio:ScholarlyWork	labeled Literature in SKG-O. GoTriple documents contain research literature, basically textual material (article, books, book parts, conference proceedings, ...)
triple:Dataset	skos:exactMatch	fabio:Dataset	labeled Research Data in SKG-O.
triple:SemanticArtefact	skos:closeMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Research Product in SKG-O. No exact correspondence in SKG-O. We can simply assess that Semantic Artefacts found in GoTriple are Research Products
triple:Multimedia	skos:closeMatch	fabio:Work	We can simply assess that Multimedia items found in GoTriple are Research Products

²⁶ <https://gotriple.eu/ontology/triple>

triple:Profile	skos:exactMatch	foaf:Agent	foaf:Agent is the superclass of both foaf:Person and foaf:Organisation. As in GoTriple we cannot do this distinction (both can be found as "authors" of metadata harvested by the platform) foaf:Agent represents the safest mapping
triple:Project	skos:closeMatch	frapo:Grant	In GoTriple there are also projects not associated with grants (e.g. Citizen Science initiatives), so the correspondence with SKG-O's Grants cannot be "exact".

Table 1: List of mappings between GoTriple data model and SKG-O.

Also, at the time of writing, GoTriple already supports SKG-IF APIs, with a first implementation of the `/Products` endpoints, by which it is possible to query and retrieve, in SKG-O compliant JSON-LD format, Documents stored in the platform's index. While limited to this single endpoint at present, GoTriple's full support of these APIs will be completed in 2026.

Also, as presented in section 4.1.1, in the course of GRAPHIA the GoTriple KG will be implemented, which will align in full with the GRAPHIA Ontology and the SKG-IF.

4.2.2. OpenCitations

Only three out of six primary SKG-IF entities are actually mapped within the OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM). These are SKG-IF Research products, SKG-IF Agent and SKG-IF Venue. However, they are mapped differently depending on the particular concept used in the OCDM to convey similar semantics. The SKG-IF types that are not considered at all are Grant, Topic and Data source.

Subject_id	Predicate_id	Target_id	Comment
fabio:Expression	skos:closeMatch	fabio:Work	OpenCitations handles directly fabio:Expression objects, which

			refers to a different (even if interrelated) FRBR concept for describing a work. However, SKG-IF enables the use of fabio:Expression objects when dealing with research product manifestations.
foaf:Agent	skos:exactMatch	foaf:Agent	OpenCitations uses the same entity specified in SKG-IF for describing agents.
fabio:Expression	skos:narrowMatch	fabio:ExpressionCollection	OpenCitations handles venues exactly at the same level of the research products they contain.

Table 2: List of mappings between OpenCitations data model and SKG-O.

4.2.3. GESIS KG

A first comparison of the GESIS KG ontology and SKG-O showed that a mapping of the core concepts seems to be feasible. Since some concepts of the GESIS KG ontology are represented by using elements from schema.org, this mapping (or parts of it) might also be reusable for other KGs. These mappings are presented in Table 3.

Subject_id	Predicate_id	Target_id	Comment
schema:Dataset	skos:exactMatch	fabio:Dataset	labeled Research Data in SKG-O
schema:ScholarlyArticle	skos:exactMatch	fabio:ScholarlyWork	labeled Literature in SKG-O
ddi:Variable	skos:closeMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Research Product in SKG-O). A (survey) variable is part of a dataset (a survey or questionnaire in these cases), so it can be seen as a research product.
ddi:Instrument	skos:closeMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Research Product in SKG-O). A (survey) instrument, e.g. a question battery, item scales, etc., is part of a dataset,

			so it can be seen as a research product.
schema:SoftwareSourceCode	skos:relatedMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Research Product in SKG-O. Software source code refers rather to programming source code, code snippets, templates, or computational methods like Machine Learning models and methods than to software applications. In GESIS KG, instances of this type are typically developed in a research context.
gesiskg:Tutorial	skos:closeMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Research Product in SKG-O. Within GESIS KG, tutorials are instructions, guidelines, and similar textual sources attached to a corresponding software source code, resp. computational method.
schema:Person	skos:exactMatch	foaf:Person	labeled Person in SKG-O
schema:Organization	skos:exactMatch	foaf:Organization	labeled Organization in SKG-O

Table 3: List of mappings between GESIS KG data model and SKG-O.

An implementation of the SKG-IF API for the GESIS KG is planned for 2026.

4.2.4. ORKG

The Open Research Knowledge Graphs is built as an effort of the scientific community, where individuals provide publications, metadata of these publications and details of the content like research field, research problem, research method, but also with individual information.

Main concepts of the SKG-O can be found in the ORKG, but due to the fact that contributors are allowed to create their own concepts duplications exist, which needs

to be eliminated in order to facilitate comprehensive mappings between the ORKG and SKG-O.

Subject_id	Predicate_id	Target_id	Comment
C14025	skos:exactMatch	fabio:Dataset	labeled Dataset in ORKG labeled Research Data in SKG-O
Dataset	skos:exactMatch	fabio:Dataset	labeled Research Data in SKG-O
Author	skos:relatedMatch	foaf:Person	labeled Person in SKG-O
Person	skos:exactMatch	foaf:Person	labeled Person in SKG-O
Paper	skos:relatedMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Research Product in SKG-O
C42000	skos:relatedMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Publication in ORKG labeled Research Product in SKG-O
C93009	skos:relatedMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Software in ORKG labeled Research Product in SKG-O
C115001	skos:relatedMatch	fabio:Work	labeled Software in ORKG labeled Research Product in SKG-O

Table 4: List of mappings between ORKG data model and SKG-O.

4.3. Implementation of the SKG-IF

To implement the first version of the GRAPHIA Ontology, we use an incremental approach based on the competency questions that were collected. A first step is to identify a set of initial competency questions to start the development of the GRAPHIA Ontology. These competency questions should be first with a low level of complexity to quickly develop a first version of the ontology and test it.

The process that we followed for this first iteration of the development is composed of two steps. First, we transform the competency question into a SPARQL query that is SKG-O compliant. During CQ-to-SPARQL transformation, we will be able to identify potentially missing concepts and relations. These missing elements are then considered for extension candidates. As we want to be as conservative as possible with SKG-O, to avoid a huge scope creep, we examined solutions leveraging the SKG-O model as such. The second step is to establish the list of SKG-IF REST API calls to evaluate the modeling choices and refine the initial mappings between the data resource model and SKG-O.

We will illustrate this process with two concrete examples of competency questions, introduced as follows:

1. Given a publication PID, find all articles that cite it, plus those cited in the publication itself
2. Given an author, return all documents where one of his/her works is cited

The approach adopted complies with the following steps.

4.3.1. SPARQL query

Assuming we have all the data from the various sources involved in GRAPHIA that are exposed within a theoretical graph compliant with SKG-O²⁷, we converted both CQs materialised with specific input information into two distinct SPARQL queries. The materialisation of the CQs we adopted for explanatory purposes are the following (the specific input is in bold):

- CQ1: Given **the publication with DOI "10.1162/qss_a_00023"**, find all articles that cite it, plus those cited in the publication itself
- CQ2: Given **the author with ORCID "0000-0003-0530-4305"**, return all documents where one of his works is cited

The two SPARQL queries that map the two natural language query above are defined as follows.

Box 1: From CQ1 to SPARQL query

²⁷ <https://w3id.org/skg-if/ontology/>

Given **the publication with DOI "10.1162/qss_a_00023"**, find all articles that cite it, plus those cited in the publication itself

Translation into SKG-O-compliant SPARQL query

```
PREFIX cito: <http://purl.org/spar/cito/>
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>
PREFIX fabio: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/>
PREFIX literal: <http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/>

SELECT DISTINCT ?article
WHERE {
    ?resprod a fabio:ScholarlyWork ;
        datacite:hasIdentifier [
            datacite:usesIdentifierScheme datacite:doi ;
            literal:hasLiteralValue "10.1162/qss_a_00023"
        ] .

    { ?resprod cito:cites ?article }
    UNION
    { ?resprod ^cito:cites ?article }
}
```

Box 2: From CQ2 to SPARQL query

Given **the author with ORCID "0000-0003-0530-4305"**, return all documents where one of his works is cited

Translation into SKG-O-compliant SPARQL query:

```
PREFIX cito: <http://purl.org/spar/cito/>
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>
PREFIX fabio: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX literal: <http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/>
PREFIX pro: <http://purl.org/spar/pro/>

SELECT DISTINCT ?article
WHERE {
    ?agent a foaf:Person ;
        datacite:hasIdentifier [
            datacite:usesIdentifierScheme datacite:orcid ;
            literal:hasLiteralValue "0000-0003-0530-4305"
        ] ;
        ^pro:isHeldBy [
```



```
    pro:withRole pro:author ;  
    ^pro:isRelatedToRoleInTime/^cito:cites ?article  
  ]  
}
```

4.3.2. SKG-IF API call

Assuming we have all the sources involved in GRAPHIA exposing their data according to the SKG-IF Open API Specification²⁸, we have devised the set of API operations that we need to call to retrieve a subset of data that is appropriate to answer the aforementioned queries. In particular:

- For CQ1: we can call the operation `/products` with the convenience filters `cf.cites_doi` and `cf.cited_by_doi` from one source dealing with tracking citation links (e.g. OpenCitations) to retrieve all the products that cite and are cited by our input article. Then, we can call the operation `/products` with the filter `identifiers.id` and `identifiers.scheme` to determine which of the returned entities from the previous call are also included in another source of interest (e.g. GoTriple).
- For CQ2: we can call the operation `/products` with the convenience filter `cf.contributions_orcid` from one source dealing with bibliographic metadata (e.g. GoTriple). Then, for each research product obtained, we call the operation `/products` with the convenience filter `cf.cites_doi` from one source dealing with tracking citation links (e.g. OpenCitations).

Supposing that the URLs to access the SKG-IF Open API endpoint for OpenCitations and GoTriple are, respectively, <https://api.opencitations.net/skg-if> and <https://api.gotriple.eu/api/skg-if/documentation>, the following set of operations are necessary to retrieving the minimal information to answer the SPARQL queries mentioned above.

SKG-IF API call to address the SPARQL query related to CQ1:

- retrieve, from OpenCitations, all the SKG-IF products that cites the one identified by the DOI “10.1162/qss_a_00023”

²⁸ <https://w3id.org/skg-if/api/skg-if-openapi.yaml>

https://api.opencitations.net/skg-if/products?filter=cf.cites_doi:10.1162/qss_a_00023

- retrieve, from OpenCitations, all the SKG-IF products that are cited by the one identified by the DOI “10.1162/qss_a_00023”

https://api.opencitations.net/skg-if/products?filter=cf.cited_by_doi:10.1162/qss_a_00023

- For each product returned in the previous calls, retrieve, from GoTriple, all available information about the particular product using its DOI as identification mechanism

https://api.gotriple.eu/api/skg-if/products?filter=identifiers.id:<product_doi>,identifiers.scheme:doi

All the products returned in the last call compose the solution space on which the SPARQL query related to CQ1 should be executed.

SKG-IF API call to address the SPARQL query related to CQ2:

- retrieve, from GoTriple, all the products where the person with ORCID “0000-0003-0530-4305” is listed as contributor

https://api.gotriple.eu/api/skg-if/products?filter=cf.contributions_orcid:0000-0003-0530-4305

- For each product returned in the previous call, retrieve, from OpenCitations, all the products that cites the one identified by the DOI of the product in consideration

https://api.opencitations.net/skg-if/products?filter=cf.cites_doi:<doi>

These two examples provide an overview of the ongoing work to develop the first version of the GRAPHIA ontology. This work is still ongoing and cannot yet be tested as none of the resources currently implement the SKG-IF REST API except for GoTriple. As of now, we do not anticipate the need to develop SKG-O extensions. However, we need to consider the various other data sources to be integrated. The following section provides a short overview of these additional resources.

4.3.3. Other resources to be integrated

Relevant data sources, the “primary sources” as well as existing SSH knowledge graphs that should be interconnected with the SSH KG have been proposed at the inception of the project. The “primary sources”, presented in the following table

(Table 5), are providing a wide range of datasets but are not implemented as Knowledge Graphs.

Data source	Data Type	Volume	Data provider	Value for research into societal challenges
GoTriple platform	Publications, datasets, profiles, projects	14 million documents, ~23.000 projects, 17 million author references from large aggregators, i.e. OpenAIRE, DOAJ, BASE, Isidore and data providers	OPERAS	SSH
RelReSearch	Primary sources, mainly manuscripts and books	70000+ records	RelReSearch	Religious studies
KU Leuven FTRW	Journal articles, posters/presentations/abstracts, archival collections, research data	~5000 records	KU Leuven FTRW, via RelReSearch	Religious studies
GGP	Browsable metadata about the Generations and Gender Surveys	Surveys from 30+ countries (~400 questions per survey)	GGP national partners	Social Science

Table 5: List of data resources to be integrated in the SSH KG and involved in the project.

Table 6 below proposed a list of Knowledge Graphs to be integrated into the SSH KG.

Data source	Data Type	Volume	Data provider	Value for research into societal challenges
Matilda ²⁹	Bibliographic metadata, authors, affiliations, citations, full-text search index, daily enriched knowledge graph	156M+ works, 12M+ authors, 30M+ indexed full text, continuously updated	Aggregates open data from major scholarly sources such as arXiv, PubMed, Crossref, RePEc, HAL, Unpaywall, ORCID, and related repositories.	Matilda offers an open, reliable alternative to commercial tools and enables large-scale analysis of publications and research trends.
EHRI Collection Graph	Archival metadata	300,000 archival descriptions, 2,200 descriptions of archival institutions, several controlled vocabularies and authority sets	EHRI	SSH and other disciplines related to Holocaust studies

Table 6: List of relevant KG to be integrated into the SSH KG.

To understand the interoperability challenges ahead and identify solutions for integrating heterogeneous data sources, we started to analyze the resources listed in table 5 and 6. What follows are the short descriptions of the above resources except GoTriple, ORKG, GESIS KG, and OpenCitation, which have been presented in details in section 4.1.

EHRI-KG

The European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI) aims to enhance access to information about Holocaust-related historical sources and promote transnational scholarship. The EHRI infrastructure is currently developing a KG based on EHRI's Portal data, in order to promote data interoperability in the field. The EHRI-KG³⁰ is

²⁹ <https://matilda.science/>

³⁰ <https://ehri-kg.ehri-project.eu/>

formalised through the EHRI Ontology³¹. The main entities of EHRI are **collection-holding institutions** and **archival materials** (record resources) related to the Holocaust, formalised in a way to be an extension of the International Council on Archives Records in Contexts Ontology (ICA RiC-O)³². It is important to point out that EHRI, which is also a GRAPHIA partner, is currently involved in an OSCARS project³³ funded initiative, which has in its plan an entire work-package dedicated to federation with other KGs (WP4: Linking EHRI entities to other KGs): specific and effective federation strategies with the SSH KG can also result from the work done in that context.

RelReSearch

RelReSearch is the discovery platform of RESILIENCE (Religious Studies Research Infrastructure), a European, cross-disciplinary research infrastructure devoted to the study of religion across academic fields. It offers a platform where disparate digital resources and databases are searchable in a unified and standardized way. It currently includes collections of **manuscripts** and **rare books** of Christian, Jewish and Muslim works from different European research institutions connected to the RESILIENCE RI^{34,35}.

RelReSearch's application profile implements a carefully selected subset of types and properties from Schema.org that are most relevant to its user community. The core supported classes include CreativeWork (with subclasses such as Article, Book, PublicationIssue, and PublicationVolume), as well as MediaObject, Person, Organization, Place, and Event. These classes are mapped from various source metadata standards - such as MARC XML, METS XML, and Dublin Core - into Schema.org, ensuring both semantic richness and cross-domain compatibility³⁶.

The RelReSearch data is available as a [Schema.org](https://schema.org) JSON-LD export, which can be provided through API or OAI-PMH for integration into the GRAPHIA KG. The biggest

³¹ <https://lod.ehri-project-test.eu/ontology/>

³² https://www.ica.org/standards/RiC/RiC-O_1-0-2.html

³³ <https://oscars-project.eu/>

³⁴ RESILIENCE RI is currently in its preparatory phase (2024-2026) and will soon evolve towards early implementation phase (2026-2028) in which extensions of RelReSearch towards the inclusion of other data types (research output, datasets, archival documents) are planned.

³⁵ <https://reiresearch.eu/#/page/aboutdatasets>

³⁶ De Leeuw, M., & Wyns, R. (2025). D2.11 Master Data Management (1-DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15599787>

challenge will be that much of the material currently in RelReSearch is represented only as the broad CreativeWork class - manuscripts and printed books - which serve as primary sources for research in religious studies. An extension of the [Schema.org](https://schema.org) based application profile to include research output - [ScholarlyArticle](#) and [Dataset](#) - is foreseen in 2026-2027 (see below in relation to 'KU Leuven FTRW').

As it is unclear if an actual KG will be implemented for RelReSearch, a reasonable integration strategy might be based on the implementation of SKG-IF compliant APIs to access its data. The alignment with this interoperability framework presents several challenges which require careful consideration to ensure a correct semantic alignment: for example, SKG-O focuses on ResearchProduct while RelReSearch provides access to resources not produced by research activities. Therefore, we may need to consider to provide a specific extension of SKG-O.

KU Leuven FTRW

KU Leuven's Faculty of Theology and Religious Studies (FTRW) plays a pivotal role as a data provider within the RESILIENCE Research Infrastructure (RI), contributing to the development and enrichment of the RelReSearch platform. At present, RelReSearch offers academic researchers, librarians, and digital humanities specialists access to nearly 70,000 **manuscripts** and **early printed books** from KU Leuven's collections, forming a substantial resource for scholarly enquiry. As part of the RESILIENCE early implementation phase, the platform will expand its scope by integrating metadata on **open access research outputs, including books, journals, and datasets**. KU Leuven FTRW will serve as the first provider to integrate research outputs into RelReSearch, thereby broadening the spectrum of accessible materials. Additionally, the **archives** curated by the Centre for the Study of the Second Vatican Council are being digitised for inclusion, further enhancing the platform's offerings. To facilitate this expansion, the RelReSearch technical team will extend its Schema.org-based application profile to accommodate new classes and properties relevant to research outputs and archival documents. Access to the KU Leuven FTRW collections will thus happen through RelReSearch. This will require developing a SKG-O extension to introduce the concept of archives, which are not produced as research outputs.

Generations and Gender Programme

The Generations and Gender Programme (GGP)³⁷ is a cross-national research infrastructure providing longitudinal survey data on life courses, family dynamics, and inter-generational and gender relations. The GGP Data Portal offers a range of **datasets**, including the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) panel study, the historic Fertility & Families Survey (FFS) from the 1990s, the Harmonized Histories dataset that provides standardized event-history data on childbearing and marriage, and a Contextual Database containing national and regional demographic, economic and policy indicators. As part of the use cases in WP3, an actual KG will be implemented for GGP, which will be based on the implementation of SKG-IF compliant APIs to access its data.

Mathilda

Matilda³⁸ is a large-scale, open bibliographic and citation knowledge base that aggregates scholarly metadata from multiple trusted sources, including arXiv, PubMed, Crossref, RePEc, HAL, Unpaywall, and numerous institutional repositories. It provides daily-updated information on more than 150 million publications, over 12 million authors, and includes an index of approximately 30 million full texts, enriched with unified identifiers, consolidated affiliation data, citation links, and a continuously updated knowledge graph. Designed as a sovereign, transparent alternative to proprietary academic search engines, Matilda enables large-scale analytics on scientific production, collaboration networks, thematic evolution, open access trends, and research inequalities. For GRAPHIA, Matilda could serve as a valuable complementary source of bibliographic and citation metadata, and should support SSH-oriented discovery, citation analyses, and the enrichment of author and publication profiles within the federated SSH Knowledge Graph.

5. Conclusions

In this document, we presented the background information relevant for this work, the conceptual design and the scope of the GRAPHIA ontology as well as our methodological approach. We also presented and described the development

³⁷ <https://www.ggp-i.org/>

³⁸ <https://matilda.science/about?l=en>

process used to build the first version of the GRAPHIA ontology based on four main initial data sources i.e. GoTriple, GESIS KG, ORKG and OpenCitations.

As the architecture design supporting the creation of the GRAPHIA SSH Knowledge Graph is based on a federative approach, we chose to leverage the existing SKG-IF Interoperability Framework and its various components. This approach will prevent us from building a global ontology for SSH which would be a daunting task due to the extreme diversity of the fields composing the domain of SSH. The GRAPHIA Ontology is therefore based on the SKG-IF ontology, SKG-O and should provide one the one hand mappings between the KG data models and SKG-O and one the other hand necessary extension of the SKG-O model to take into account the diversity of resources to be added to the GRAPHIA SSH KG.

This specific technical choice required us to dive into the SKG-IF in more detail and to work on the alignment of four existing knowledge graphs. Furthermore, we spend a lot of effort in identifying relevant cross-KG competency questions to test and validate the ontology and our approach. A large fraction of our effort has been dedicated to the analysis of the 70 collected CQs. Unfortunately, the current KGs, although mature production KGs, do not yet offer an implementation of the SKG-IF REST API, which prevents us from further testing the integration of the different KGs.

The first version of the GRAPHIA ontology is therefore limited and will be extended in the following phases of the GRAPHIA project. It is important to mention that, to support the integration of the various KGs considered in GRAPHIA during the course of the project, we decided to extend the initial duration of the task until month 30 of the project instead of the initial deadline of month 12. This will enable us to provide support to the KG developed in the context of GRAPHIA and establish a set of initial extensions.

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Appendix A.

The table below contains all the competency questions collected with, when available, the Knowledge Graph involved and the level of priority. The analysis of the CQs is an iterative process as we are constantly collecting new Competency Questions. When the CQs have been analysed but not prioritised, we specify it in the table with N/A.

CQ Id	CQ	Graph involved	Priority
CQ_001	Given a publication PID, find all articles that cite it plus those cited in the publication itself	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTriple	High
CQ_002	Given an author, return all documents where one of his/her work is cited	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTriple	High
CQ_003	Give me the list of identifiers of all the available datasets that i can find in this "federation" of graph related to topic X and keywords Y	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTriple	High
CQ_004	I want to discover all publications that are available as open access related to topics x and keywords y throughout different KG.	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTriple	N/A
CQ_005	I need to extract all documents, facts, etc, that refer a specific geographic area, identified by a name (e.g. a region or a town), so that I can crosslink with Genius Loci datasets	GESIS KG, GoTriple	Low
CQ_006	Authors deduplication: I just need to make sure if two or more authors are actually the same person or not, by checking the attribution of documents provided by all the graphs of the federation	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTriple	Low
CQ_007	Given the PID of a publication, I want to align its bibliographic metadata	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	High

	across graphs, by also removing duplicated elements		
CQ_008	I want to discover related resources in other knowledge graphs based on matching PIDs, Named Entities, and keywords, so I can extend my own database with this information.	GESIS KG, OpenCitation	N/A
CQ_009	Which social science datasets from GESIS are cited by articles in OpenCitations?	ORKG, GESIS KG	Medium
CQ_010	Which ORKG comparisons include contributions that make use of datasets registered in GESIS?	ORKG, GESIS KG, OpenCitation	Medium
CQ_011	What is the citation impact (OpenCitations) of contributions referring dataset X (GESIS) across different ORKG comparisons?	ORKG, OpenCitation	High
CQ_012	Which research contributions (ORKG) have received the most citations (OpenCitations) in the past five years?	ORKG, GESIS KG	Low
CQ_013	Which ORKG-described research contributions make use of datasets stored in GESIS?	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_014	what are the topics and scientific domains covered in these graphs?	OpenCitation, GESIS KG	High
CQ_015	Most common sampling procedures (GESIS) for (specific subject/domain) ecological based on the most cited paper (OpenCitations) from European universities after 202X	ORKG, GESIS KG, OpenCitation	Medium
CQ_016	Are there citations matching titles and authors but mismatching formatting/information provided (for example missing DOIs) compatibilities	OpenCitation, GESIS KG	Medium

CQ_017	I have to do research in [domain] using [specific methodology]. List highest citations matching these combinations, prioritising newest contributions.	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG	High
CQ_018	Which authors act as 'bridges' across the graphs? (eg appears in ORKG entries and publish highly cited works in OpenCitations that reuse GESIS data)	ORKG, GESIS KG	High
CQ_019	Give the publications referring to digital documentation techniques	GESIS KG, OpenCitation	Medium
CQ_020	Which datasets related to climate change listed in Gesis have been cited in research papers by OpenCitations	ORKG, GESIS KG	Medium
CQ_021	How do different research studies, as documented in ORKG, compare and contrast the climate change datasets listed in GESIS	ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Low
CQ_022	I have to do a research on a specific place, or a specific geographic area, defined by keywords, and I need a dataset for a specific subject, also defined by keywords. Give me the references of all the available datasets for that place and subject that are present in all the graphs	ORKG, GESIS KG	High
CQ_023	Given a keyword K, what are the most common keywords that appear in papers having K?	ORKG, GESIS KG, OpenCitation	Medium
CQ_024	I want to know what authors are most key to reading in relation to topic x and who generally publish in immediate open access. (note all GESIS publications are open access)	ORKG, GESIS KG, OpenCitation, GoTRIPLE	High
CQ_025	Given a specific output produced by a diagnostic instrument, which other	ORKG, GESIS KG,	Low

	data across different knowledge graphs show analogies or similar patterns, what interpretative meaning has been assigned to them, and what supporting documentation has been provided?	OpenCitation, E-RIHS Digilab KG	
CQ_026	Given a [specific research question related to diagnostic investigations on cultural heritage], what are the main methodologies adopted by the scientific community that have been reused the most?	ORKG, GESIS KG, OpenCitation, E-RIHS Digilab KG	Low
CQ_027	Given a specific artwork (let's say Michelangelo's David in the Accademia in Florence) what are all the publications/dataset/digital items that refer to it?	GoTRIPLE, OpenCitation, ORKG, E-RHIS' DIGILAB KG	N/A
CQ_028	I want to know which authors have published about feminism	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE, Matilda KG	Medium
CQ_029	I want to get the list of publications about ecology and republicanism	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE, Matilda KG	Medium
CQ_030	give the countries where the topic X has been most addressed in publications	OpenCitation, GoTRIPLE, ORKG, GESIS KG	Medium
CQ_031	Give a citation list of papers researching prompt engineering for LLM, newest to oldest	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_032	I want to know in which scientific domains, the concept "information" has been mostly discussed		Medium

CQ_033	Give the publications that have an abstract accessible in [Ukrainian]	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_034	Which [region/country/continent] university produces the highest number of citations regarding [x research topic]	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_035	For a {set of keywords}, give me the references of all datasets, articles and researches with that {set of keywords} and their respective numbers.	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_036	Give the keywords that have been mostly used in queries with this one [X]	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_037	Give the PIDs of all the resources that are linked to this researcher / this research center?	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_038	Give the researchers that are mostly cited by this author	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_039	Give the researchers that have published with this author	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_040	I want to know which datasets have been published between [year] and [year] about this X topic	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_041	I want to know which topics have been mainly addressed between [year] and [year] in this geographical area / in this language	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_042	Give the list of the datasets that have reused the following dataset X	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_043	I want the list of journal papers which metadata consist the keywords {diamond oa, diamond Open Access model, Diamond business model}	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium

CQ_044	I want to know which are the publications that have been mostly downloaded this last 24 hours	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_045	Which authors have published several thesis (in this scientific domain)	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_046	I want to know which authors have published more than one version of their book (i.e 2 or 3 versions)	OpenCitation, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_047	I want to know which are the datasets about the usage of soft mobility vehicles in a city	GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE, ORKG	Medium
CQ_048	I want to know which are the resources (researchers, datasets, publications) addressing judgement of political people while they still have political responsibility	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG	Medium
CQ_049	I want to know which resources addressed new technologies and ethics all together?	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	N/A
CQ_050	I want to know which publications do we have on innovative HR management	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_051	Which resources in the system identify societal issues linked to the SDGs for a specific geographic area (e.g., city, country, or region)?	OpenCitation, ORKG, GoTRIPLE, GESIS KG, EHRI Collection Graph	High
CQ_052	Which countries have research initiatives or outputs addressing specific SDGs?	GESIS KG	Low
CQ_053	What kinds of research activities linked to the SDGs are being funded in each country, and by which organisations?	GESIS KG	Low

CQ_054	Which outputs in the system are classified under Library and Information Science?	GoTRIPLE, GESIS KG, ORKG	High
CQ_055	Which publishers and journals are most active in disseminating research on LIS?	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTriple	Low
CQ_056	Which authors are most frequently publishing on these topics?	GESIS KG, ORKG, GoTRIPLE	High
CQ_058	I want to know which monographs have been classified under more than 3 different disciplines	ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_059	I want to search for projects' results (reports, deliverables, recommendations) that contain the {set of keywords}	GoTRIPLE	Medium
CQ_060	I want to find research papers (articles, books) that contain a set of keywords and were funded by the Horizon project	GoTRIPLE	High
CQ_061	Given a scientific publication PID, retrieve all sentences citing another work and classify the citation intent (e.g., Background, Method, Result Comparison, Critique, Future Work)	GESIS KG, ORKG, OpenCitation	N/A
CQ_062	For a given keyword or subject in English, find its equivalent terms in other languages across the federated graphs.	GESIS KG, GoTriple, E-RIHS Digilab KG	N/A
CQ_063	Given a dataset PID, list all publications, projects, and datasets that reused or cited it, with timestamps and reuse type (direct, derived, referenced).	OpenCitation, ORKG, GESIS KG, GoTriple	N/A
CQ_064	Given an entity (e.g., a researcher, place, or institution), find its equivalent URIs across all federated	GESIS KG, ORKG, GoTriple,	N/A

	KGs and identify alignment confidence.	EHRI Collection Graph	
CQ_065	Given a topic keyword, how has its occurrence evolved across years in SSH publications and datasets?	OpenCitation, GESIS KG, GoTriple, ORKG	N/A
CQ_066	How does the concept “X” (e.g., “democracy”) differ semantically across languages and time in SSH publications?	GESIS KG, GoTriple	N/A
CQ_067	What is the gender distribution of first authors in publications on topic Y between 2010 and 2025?	ORKG, GESIS KG, OpenCitation	N/A
CQ_068	Given a geographic location, retrieve all research resources (publications, datasets, archival materials) from different SSH disciplines – e.g. ethnomusicology, anthropology, folklore studies – that describe or analyse cultural practices in that location, regardless of the ethnic/language group studied.	GESIS KG, GoTriple, EHRI Collection Graph	N/A
CQ_069	For a given keyword, retrieve all publications that have associated audio resources – whether embedded in the publication, linked as supplementary files, or published separately in archives, datasets, or media repositories.	GoTriple, GESIS KG, OpenCitation, ORKG, EHRI Collection Graph, Matilda KG, E-RIHS Digilab KG, Resilience	N/A
CQ_070	Given a publication, retrieve all audio recordings it cites, describes, or refers to (e.g. through performer names, ensemble names, recording titles, or cited media), and identify	GoTriple, GESIS KG, EHRI Collection Graph, Resilience	N/A

	these recordings across all available datasets and archives.		
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